

Electrode kinetics and thermodynamics of Mn^{II} complexes with some amino acids and vitamin-B₇

Afroza Khanam and Farid Khan*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 22 August 2008, revised 23 March 2009, accepted 24 March 2009

Abstract : The paper presents simple and highly sensitive direct voltammetric method developed for the determination of stability of the ternary complexes of Mn^{II} complexes with L-lysine, L-ornithine, L-threonine, L-serine, L-glutamic acid and L-aspartic acid as primary ligands and vitamin-B₇ (biotin) as secondary ligand at pH 7.30 ± 0.01 and μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄ at 25 °C and 35 °C. The nature of current voltage curves was quasireversible and diffusion controlled. Mn^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with these drugs as confirmed by Schaap and McMaster method. The sequence of stability constant of complexes was L-lysine < L-ornithine < L-threonine < L-serine < L-glutamic acid < L-aspartic acid can be explained on the basis of size, basicity and steric hindrance of ligands. The study has been carried out at 35 °C also to determine the thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy change (ΔH), free energy change (ΔG) and entropy change (ΔS) respectively. The kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ), diffusion coefficient (D^{1/2}) and standard rate constant (k) were calculated. The values of 'α' confirmed that the 'activated complex' is formed in an exact intermediate between dropping mercury electrode and mercury solution interface. The study confirmed that L-amino acids or vitamin-B₇ or the combination of both could be used as antidote against Mn^{II} toxicity.

Keywords : Electrode kinetics, thermodynamics, [Mn-L-amino acidate-vitamin-B₇] system.

Introduction

Amino acids are well known chelating agents and play important role in biology, pharmacy and industry¹⁻³. Complexes of some metal ions with amino acids can be used as models to study the pharmaco-dynamic effects of drugs or for increasing the biocompatibility and minimize the toxic effects of some metal ions⁴. Vitamin-B₇ (biotin or vitamin H)⁵ is a member of the vitamin B complex and water-soluble. Biotin is involved in energy metabolism and plays a role in enabling the body to use glucose⁶. Biotin is sometimes chemically linked to a molecule or protein for biochemical assays⁷, earned a keen attention towards the studies of their metal complexes. Manganese is an essential trace element in biology⁸. Manganese works with vitamin K to support blood clotting, aids in digestion, and as antioxidant. It is a vital component of Sodium Oxide Dismutase⁹ and it exhibits complex reduction-oxidation (redox) chemistry¹⁰⁻¹³. Concern over possible neurotoxic effects associated with chronic exposure to moderate levels of manganese in mixed oxidation states and by the growing use of methylcyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl, a manganese-containing antiknock

additive in gasoline is currently used in a number of developed countries¹⁴. Furthermore, epidemiologic studies have suggested a relationship between elevated environmental manganese exposure and an increased risk for parkinsonian disturbances^{15,16}.

The elevated concentration of Mn^{II} can be reduced by chelation therapy¹⁷. Therefore, the present study has been undertaken in which complexes of Mn^{II} with L-amino acids and vitamin-B₇ has been studied. The specificity of the drugs and its amount is stability constants dependent therefore, the same has also been determined. Thermodynamic parameters play important role to confirm whether a particular reaction is feasible or not under the given set of conditions therefore, the same have also been undertaken. Kinetic parameters confirm the nature of electrode process at DME has also been discussed.

Results and discussion

Mn^{II} gave two electron quasireversible reduction wave at pH 7.30 ± 0.01, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄ at 25 °C. The nature of current-voltage curves for complexes is also quasireversible. The E_{1/2} values became more negative

with addition of vitamin-B₇ to the [Mn-L-amino acids] system which showed ternary complex formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 stoichiometries. Gelling¹⁹ method was used to determine the values of $E_{1/2}^{\text{reversible}}$ form $E_{1/2}^{\text{quasireversible}}$ by plotting $(E - RT/nF \log i_d - i/i)$ vs i for all the complexes. To know the values of β_{11} and β_{12} , the study has been carried out at two constant concentrations of vitamin-B₇ i.e. 0.025 M and 0.050 M respectively. The values of stability constant of complexes were given in Table 1. The data and plots of $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ against $[X]$ (where F_{ij} is a Schaap and McMaster²⁰ function to evaluate the stability constant β_{ij} , X = L-lysine, Y = vitamin-B₇ and i and j are their stoichiometric numbers respectively) for [Mn-L-lysinate-vitamin-B₇] system were given in Table 2, Fig. 1 respectively. These functions

were used to determine the stability constant of complexes.

The stability of mixed ligand complexes can be compared with binary complexes to calculate the values of mixing constant $\log K_m$ by the eq. (1)²⁰.

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}] \quad (1)$$

The values of $\log K_m$ were 0.535, 0.640, 3.375, 1.080, 0.255, 0.340 respectively for [Mn-L-lys-vit.-B₇], [Mn-L-orn-vit.-B₇], [Mn-L-thr-vit.-B₇], [Mn-L-ser-vit.-B₇], [Mn-L-glu-vit.-B₇] and [Mn-L-asp-vit.-B₇] systems. The positive values of $\log K_m$ indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes, while the negative values indicate that the binary complexes are more stable than the ternary complexes.

Table 1. Stability constants of ternary complexes
Mn^{II} = 0.50 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.3 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25 °C

Drug	$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{10}^{26}$	$\log \beta_{20}^{26}$	$\log \beta_{30}^{26}$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
L-Lysine	-	-	2.36	4.62	6.23	4.20	-	9.85
L-Ornithine	-	-	2.93	4.75	6.61	4.37	7.37	10.07
L-Threonine	-	-	3.55	-	6.93	4.73	7.43	-
L-Serine	-	-	3.82	4.91	-	4.89	7.65	10.55
L-Glutamic acid	-	-	4.20	7.30	9.93	5.26	8.00	10.65
L-Aspartic acid	-	-	4.25	7.45	10.00	5.42	8.22	10.87
Vitamin-B ₇	1.80	2.71						

(biotin, vitamin H)

$\log \beta_{10} = \pm 0.01 - \pm 0.02$, $\log \beta_{20} = \pm 0.02$, $\log \beta_{30} = \pm 0.01$, $\log \beta_{11} = \pm 0.01$, $\log \beta_{12} = \pm 0.02$, $\log \beta_{21} = \pm 0.02$, $\sigma_{\beta_{10}} = 0.745$, $\sigma_{\beta_{20}} = 1.436$, $\sigma_{\beta_{30}} = 1.436$, $\sigma_{\beta_{11}} = 1.865$, $\sigma_{\beta_{12}} = 0.367$, $\sigma_{\beta_{21}} = 0.423$.

Table 2. Polarographic data and $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ values of [Mn-L-lysinate-vitamin-B₇] system
Mn^{II} = 0.50 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25 °C

[L-Lys] × 10 ⁻³ M	[Vitamin-B ₇] = 0.025 M (fixed)						[Vitamin-B ₇] = 0.05 M (fixed)					
	$E_{1/2}^{\text{r}}$ V vs SCE	$\log i_m/i_c$	$F_{00}[X, Y]$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁴	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁷	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁵	$E_{1/2}^{\text{r}}$ V vs SCE	$\log i_m/i_c$	$F_{00}[X, Y]$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁴	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁷	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁵
0.00	1.400	-	-	-	-	-	1.40	-	-	-	-	-
0.50	1.449	0.0074	47.48	8.916	177.037	19.95	1.458	0.0074	94.46	17.80	35.4024	19.95
1.00	1.466	0.0149	180.58	17.768	177.038	19.94	1.475	0.0149	360.50	35.50	35.4025	19.94
2.00	1.484	0.0226	712.35	35.472	177.040	19.95	1.493	0.0226	1423.63	70.90	35.4026	19.93
3.00	1.494	0.0304	1598.22	53.177	177.042	19.93	1.503	0.0304	3194.82	106.31	35.4028	19.94
4.00	1.501	0.0384	2838.20	70.882	177.044	19.94	1.512	0.0384	6712.30	141.71	35.4030	19.94
5.00	1.506	0.0465	4432.29	88.588	177.046	19.95	1.515	0.0465	8861.48	177.12	35.4032	19.93
6.00	1.511	0.0548	6380.52	106.293	177.048	19.94	1.520	0.0548	12756.95	212.52	35.4034	19.94
8.00	1.518	0.0632	11339.43	141.706	177.052	19.95	1.527	0.0632	22672.28	283.33	35.4038	19.95
10.00	1.524	0.0632	17715.02	177.121	177.056	19.94	1.532	0.0718	35420.16	354.14	35.4042	19.94
20.00	1.541	0.0718	70846.43	354.217	177.076	19.95	1.550	0.0718	141651.45	708.23	35.4062	19.93
30.00	1.552	0.0718	159409.06	531.353	177.096	19.94	1.561	0.0718	318711.26	1062.35	35.4082	19.93

$\log A = 0.46$, $\log B = 2.811$, $\log C = 8.25$, $\log D = 6.30$

$\log A = 0.73$, $\log B = 3.02$, $\log C = 8.55$, $\log D = 6.30$

$(E_{1/2}^{\text{r}}) = \pm 0.0001 - \pm 0.0003$, $\sigma E_{1/2}^{\text{r}} = 0.041$.

Fig. 1. Plot of $F_{ij}[X,Y]$ vs $[X]$ for $[Mn-L-lysinate-vitamin-B_7]$ system.

Trend of stability of ternary complexes :

The sequence of stability constants of complexes with respect to ligands is L-lys < L-orn, L-thr < L-ser < L-glu < L-asp. It has been observed that as the size of amino acids increased, the stability of its complexes decreased²¹. The stability of L-amino acid complex also depends upon the chelate ring formation and basicities of ligands²². In this study, the stability of lysinate complex is minimum owing to the lowest pK value of L-lysine as expected²³. In case of L-serine and L-threonine, the stability of the later is less than the L-serine complex owing to the fact that electron withdrawing OH⁻ group is nearer to L-threoninate complex than L-serinate complex, causing greater repulsive forces between metal and OH⁻ group in L-threonine complexes than L-serine complexes. The higher stability of L-aspartate complexes than L-glutamate complex is obvious from the chelate ring formation. In these amino acids, the aspartate forms one five- and one six-membered rings with the metal while L-glutamate forms

one six- and one seven-membered ring. As the size of ring in amino acid increases, the stability of complex decreases²⁴. The stabilities of L-glutamate and L-aspartate complexes are greater than those of the L-lysinate, L-ornithinate, L-threoninate, L-serinate complexes due to large difference in their basic strength²⁵ and the same is evident from pK values of L-amino acids²⁶.

In case of vitamin-B₇, nitrogen and oxygen of uriedoyl group may take part in bond formation with Mn^{II}. It is clear from the values of stability constant of the complexes that vitamin-B₇ and amino acids used either singly or simultaneously might be effective to reduce the toxicity of metal *in vivo*¹⁷.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The kind of complex species that can be measured with a mercury electrode depends on thermodynamic aspects²⁷. Thermodynamic parameters such as enthalpy change (ΔH), free energy change (ΔG) and entropy change (ΔS) of the complexes have been calculated by the thermodynamic eqs. (2), (3) and (4)²⁸.

$$\Delta H = 2.303 RT_1 T_2 (\log \beta_2 - \log \beta_1) / T_2 - T_1 \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (4)$$

It is clear from the values of ΔS , ΔG and ΔH in Table 3 that the values of ΔS are more negative at higher temperature and ΔG are less negative at higher temperature confirming that the complexes are not stable at higher temperature²⁹. The negative values of ΔH show that reactions are exothermic in nature.

Kinetic parameters :

The kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ) and standard rate constant (k) were determined by Tamamushi and Tanaka method³⁰ by plotting $(E - RT/nF \log i_d - i/i)$ against i and $\log(Z - 1)$ against $(E^{T_{1/2}} - E)$ for $[Mn-L-lysinate-vitamin-B_7]$ system.

The values of kinetic parameters were given in Table 4. It is obvious from the value of α that the values varied from $[Mn-L-lysinate-vitamin-B_7]$ 0.36 to 0.55 (about 0.50), and value of α for other systems were also about 0.50, which confirmed that 'transition state' lies midway between dropping mercury electrode and solution interface. The values of rate constant (k) varied from $2.81 \times$

Table 3. Stability constant and thermodynamic parameters of ternary complexes of [Mn-L-aminoacidate-vitamin-B₇] system at 25 °C and 35 °C

System	Stability constants			-ΔH kcal/mol			-ΔG kcal/mol			-ΔS kcal/mol		
	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
	25/35 °C	25/35°C	25/35°C	(35-25 °C)			25/35 °C	25/35°C	25/35°C	25/35 °C	25/35°C	25/35°C
	for difference of 10 °C											
Mn-L-lysinate- vitamin-B ₇	4.20	-	9.85	8.400	-	17.640	5.727	-	13.432	8.9692	-	14.1220
	4.00	-	9.43				5.6376	-	13.291	8.9695	-	14.1227
Mn-L-ornithinate- vitamin-B ₇	4.37	7.37	10.07	15.792	15.540	14.364	5.9674	10.0502	13.7348	32.9698	18.4235	2.1126
	4.00	7.00	9.73				5.6376	9.8658	13.7135	32.9701	18.4239	2.1132
Mn-L-threoninate- vitamin-B ₇	4.73	7.43	-	13.860	13.860	-	6.4501	10.1319	-	24.8665	12.5112	-
	4.40	7.10	-				6.2014	10.0067	-	24.8668	12.5117	-
Mn-L-serinate- vitamin-B ₇	4.89	7.65	10.55	16.632	18.984	14.700	6.6765	10.4347	14.3866	33.4091	28.6904	1.0528
	4.50	7.20	10.20				6.3423	10.1477	14.3759	33.4094	28.6908	1.0535
Mn-L-glutamate- vitamin-B ₇	5.26	8.00	10.65	15.120	11.340	18.900	7.1729	10.9093	14.5229	26.6695	1.4463	14.6895
	4.90	7.73	10.20				6.9061	10.8947	14.3759	26.6698	1.4468	14.6902
Mn-L-aspartate- vitamin-B ₇	5.42	8.22	10.87	13.692	13.524	15.624	7.3993	11.2120	14.8257	21.1178	7.7594	2.6800
	5.10	7.90	10.50				7.1879	11.1343	14.7987	21.1181	7.7599	2.6808

ΔH = ±0.0002, ΔG = ±0.0002, ΔS = ±0.0002; σ₁₁ΔH = 2.926, σ₁₂ΔH = 2.847, σ₂₁ΔH = 1.956; σ₁₁ΔG = 0.630, σ₁₂ΔG = 0.509, σ₂₁ΔG = 0.556; σ₁₁ΔS = 7.402, σ₁₂ΔS = 9.818, σ₂₁ΔS = 6.459.

Table 4. Kinetic parameters of [Mn-L-lysinate-vitamin-B₇] system
Mn^{II} = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25 °C

[L-Lys] × 10 ⁻³	√[Vitamin-B ₇] = 0.025 M						[Vitamin-B ₇] = 0.05 M					
	(E _{1/2}) ^{qr} -V vs SCE	Slope (mV)	α	λ (s ^{-1/2})	D ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	k × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)	(E _{1/2}) ^{qr} -V vs SCE	Slope (mV)	α	λ (s ^{-1/2})	D ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm ² s ^{-1/2})	k × 10 ³ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.00	1.410	38	0.393	1.702	3.8879	6.6186	1.410	38	0.4288	2.4046	3.8879	9.3490
0.50	1.453	37	0.449	1.517	3.8220	5.7988	1.461	38	0.5502	1.0740	3.8220	4.1052
1.00	1.469	37	0.437	1.517	3.7561	5.6988	1.478	37	0.4645	2.4046	3.7561	9.0321
2.00	1.491	38	0.406	1.702	3.6902	6.2820	1.496	38	0.4951	1.5172	3.6902	5.5989
3.00	1.497	39	0.505	1.517	3.6243	5.4989	1.508	39	0.5057	1.0740	3.6243	3.8929
4.00	1.507	37	0.477	1.352	3.5584	4.8118	1.515	39	0.4288	1.5172	3.5584	5.3989
5.00	1.509	38	0.500	1.517	3.4925	5.2989	1.519	39	0.5057	1.2051	3.4925	4.2091
6.00	1.517	39	0.555	1.074	3.4266	3.6806	1.524	38	0.5086	0.8531	3.4266	2.9236
8.00	1.522	38	0.357	1.702	3.3607	5.7211	1.531	38	0.4860	1.3522	3.3607	4.5444
10.00	1.529	37	0.464	1.205	3.2948	3.9708	1.537	37	0.5086	1.0740	3.3607	3.6098
20.00	1.547	38	0.411	1.517	3.2948	4.9990	1.556	37	0.5288	0.8531	3.2948	2.8111
30.00	1.557	38	0.505	0.957	3.2948	3.1541	1.566	39	0.4708	1.2051	3.2948	3.9708

(E_{1/2})^{qr} = ±0.003, k = ±0.002, σ(E_{1/2})^{qr} = 0.041, σk = 1.057

10⁻³ to 9.35 × 10⁻³ cm s⁻¹ confirmed that the electrode process were quasireversible. The values of diffusion coefficient (D^{1/2}) as determined by Ilkovic equation³¹ were as expected.

In present study, we report here the interaction of Mn^{II} with L-amino acids and vitamin-B₇ at pH 7.30 ± 0.01 was investigated using simple DC polarography. The

results indicated that current voltage curves were quasireversible and diffusion controlled in 1.0 M NaClO₄ at pH 7.30 ± 0.01 and temperature 25 °C and 35 °C. The stability constants varied from 1.80 to 10.87 which are quite reasonable and therefore, either L-amino acids alone or vitamin-B₇ alone or in combination or in the form of metal complex could be effective against Mn toxicity¹⁷. The negative values of ΔH indicated the exo-

thermic nature of the metal-ligand interaction. The complexes were not stable at higher temperature was confirmed by the values of ΔG and ΔS of complexes at higher temperature. The values of transfer coefficient (α) varied from 0.36 to 0.55 (0.50) showed that the 'transition state' behaves between oxidant and reductant response to applied potential and it lies in the midpoint of dropping mercury electrode and solution interface. The values of rate constant (k) varied from 2.81×10^{-3} to 9.35×10^{-3} cm s⁻¹ confirmed the quasireversible nature of electrode processes.

Experimental

Electrochemical experiment (simple DC polarography) was carried out using a manual polarograph using a (Toshniwal PL-50) polyflex galvanometer. The polarographic cell was of Latinen and Lingane type in which polarographic capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mm in diameter was used. The $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ value was 2.40 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/2} at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury. A Systronic pH meter 361 was used to measure the pH of the analyte at 7.30 ± 0.01 .

The following chemicals were used for all polarographic experiments : HClO₄ (Sigma), NaOH (Sigma), NaClO₄ (Fluka), Triton X-100 (Aldrich), MnCl₂ (B.D.H.), L-amino acids (Lobachem) and vitamin-B₇ (biotin or vitamin H) (Fluka) and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The purity of L-amino acids was checked by chromatographic method³². Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the analyte for deoxygenation before recording the current-voltage data. The pH of the analyte at 7.30 ± 0.01 was adjusted by using dilute solutions of HClO₄ or NaOH as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte.

Polarographic studies of the ternary complexes of Mn^{II} with some amino acids and vitamin-B₇ (biotin or vitamin H) were recorded using depolarizer and ligands (L-amino acids and vitamin-B₇) in ratio 1 : 40 : 40 and the concentration of amino acids varied from 0.5 mM to 30.0 mM at two fixed concentrations of vitamin-B₇ (biotin or vitamin H) i.e. 0.025 M and 0.050 M. It has been observed that $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative side with increase in concentration of L-amino acids. The current-voltage curves were obtained at different pH values. It has been ob-

served that the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was obtained within the pH range 7.10–8.50, but pH 7.30 was selected for studying the complexes³³. The concentrations of metal, NaClO₄ and Triton X-100 (suppressor) in test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001 % respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head of the Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for providing the laboratory facilities.

References

1. J. Brosnan, *J. Nutr.*, 2000, **130**, 988.
2. K. Pisrewicz, D. Mora, F. Pflueger, G. Fields and F. Mari, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 6207.
3. G. Wu, Y. Fang, S. Yang, J. Luptan and N. Turner, *J. Nutr.*, 2004, **134**, 489.
4. El-Said Asma, S. A. Zidan Amna, S. El-Meligy Mahmoud, A. Aly Aref, Omar and F. Mohamened, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 633.
5. D. M. Mock, J. G. Quirk and N. I. Mock, *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 2002, **75**, 295.
6. M. Maebashi, Y. Makino and Y. Furukawa, *J. Clin. Biochem. Nutr.*, 1993, **14**, 218.
7. V. E. Colombo, F. Gerber and M. Bronhofer, *J. Am. Acad. Dermatol.*, 1990, **23**, 1132.
8. C. F. Yocum and V. L. Pecoraro, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.*, 1999, **3**, 182.
9. Y. Anjaneyulu and R. P. Rao, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1986, **16**, 257.
10. S. H. Reaney, G. Bench and D. R. Smith, *Toxicol. Sci.*, 2006, **93**, 114.
11. M. Gupta and M. N. Srivastava, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1991, 859.
12. V. K. Saxena, M. Gupta and M. N. Srivastava, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1996, **26**, 1661.
13. M. R. Ullah and P. K. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 150.
14. T. Ressler, J. Wong, J. Roos and I. L. Smith, *Sci. Technol.*, 2000, **34**, 950.
15. R. H. Gwiazda, D. Lee, J. Sheridan and D. R. Smith, *Neurotoxicology*, 2002, **95**, 1.
16. F. M. Corrigan, L. Murray, C. L. Wyatt and R. F. Shore, *Exp. Neurol.*, 1998, **150**, 339.
17. M. D. Walker and D. R. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 1186.
18. A. A. Khan and W. U. Malik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 565.
19. S. N. Chadar and F. Khan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 1242.

20. F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2003, 19, 283.
21. P. J. Gelling, *Z. Electrochem. Ber. Bunsenges, Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 477; 1963, 67, 799.
22. W. B. Schaap and D. L. McMaster, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
23. R. C. Kapoor and B. S. Agarawal, "Principles of Polarography", Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1991, 71.
24. R. Dodke and F. Khan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, 70, 15.
25. S. Vajhallya and F. Khan, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1999, 72, 397.
26. S. Vajhallya and F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2000, 16, 311.
27. A. E. Martell and M. Calvin, "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice-Hall Inc., New York, 1952, 155.
28. B. V. Mrudula Rao, S. J. Swamy and P. Lingaiah, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 887.
29. B. L. Lewis, G. W. Luther, H. Lane and T. M. Church, *J. Electroanal.*, 1995, 7, 166.
30. J. C. F. Rossotti and H. Rossotti, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw Hill Book Co., London, 1961.
31. F. Khan and A. V. Mahajani, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 16, 165; F. Khan and A. Zaidi, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1999, 16, 10.
32. R. Tamamushi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neufolge*, 1963, 39, 117; R. Tamamushi, K. Ishibashi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neufolge*, 1962, 35, 211.
33. D. Ilkovic, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1936, 8, 13.